

Smart textiles based on triboelectric nanogenerators: Deposition of laser-assisted conductive graphene electrodes and energy-harvesting layers by industrially relevant, sustainable processes

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INTRODUCTION

Current graphene production methods face challenges in achieving reliable, green, and large-scale production of graphene-coated textiles and flexible substrates. Most techniques use chemically derived graphene powders that are not easily soluble in environmentally friendly solvents like water. In the e-textile industry, wet-chemistry methods are prevalent, depositing a graphene oxide (GO) layer that is later converted to reduced graphene oxide (rGO) on textiles. In this study, we introduce an **environmentally friendly technique** for depositing high-quality graphene employing laser-assisted method.

AIM: Optimization of a **waste-free** process under ambient conditions, facilitating the laser-assisted conversion of raw materials into turbostratic few-layer graphene.

RAW MATERIALS

- Polyester (PES) and polyamide (PA) fabrics provided by BORN
- GO water dispersion (0.4 wt% Concentration) by Graphenea

RESULTS

Graphene layer

(Left) Representative Raman spectrum of rGO on textiles by direct laser-assisted reduction. (Right) Scanning electron microscope image of textiles fibers coated by graphene layers

Dielectric layer

PA: Treated PA shows increase in Air Permeability. Possible plasma Etching or simply elongation of the fabric during treatment resulting in pore widening
PES: No significant change in air permeability after treatment. Subtle decrease in air permeability after coating deposition.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS

→ An optimized dielectric layer was applied to the graphene-treated textiles, serving as triboelectric-based energy harvesting layer.

CHARACTERIZATION

The graphene film morphology and the produced graphene quality were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Raman spectroscopy.

The textiles lifetime was investigated by performing coating adhesion on graphene coated textiles and fibers, high abrasion resistance, durability (washability) and breathability.

PROCESS OVERVIEW

CONCLUSIONS

- A single-step, eco-friendly technique for depositing high-quality graphene utilizing laser-assisted methods was established.
- This technique results in the direct formation of low-sheet resistance (R_s) graphene on the textile surface.
- The developed TENG structures demonstrate highly favorable energy harvesting properties suitable for biomechanical energy conversion, while also possessing both flexibility and durability.

The laser-assisted method upscaled to a pilot R2R line

